

Generalized Time Reversal Elastic Scattering Balance and Statistical Mechanics

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Feb. 27, 2020

In previous notes, we argued the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB), Fermi-Dirac (FD) and Bose-Einstein (BE) distributions may be obtained by a time reversal elastic two body scattering balance. This approach does not require counting, any notion of entropy or partition functions. The basic ideas for the MB case is to use $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$ ((1a)) and $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ ((1b)) where $f(e)$ is the distribution function. Taking \ln of ((1a)) and equating to ((1b)) yields the MB distribution. For the FD and BE cases, ((1a)) is modified to account for scattering restrictions or enhancements. In this note, we wish to consider a more generalized case. We first consider that ((1a)) does not hold for MB type particles, but rather that $g(f(e_1)) g(f(e_2)) = g(f(e_3)) g(f(e_4))$ ((2)) is in place. Conservation of energy is retained. This leads to issues with the usual ensemble approach which leads to the canonical (and grand canonical) partition functions via saddle point integration and Shannon's entropy. As a result, a new type of entropy may be needed. In addition, we consider ((2)) modified for the FD and BE cases.

Generalized MB Equilibrium

It seems one may obtain the MB distribution by taking the \ln of $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$ and equating to $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. Conservation of energy ensures that overall no energy is lost or gained in the gas. In addition, ((1a)) holds for a very specific orientation of momenta. For the sake of argument, one may imagine the probability for a two body reaction between $f(e_1)$ and $f(e_2)$ is not $f(e_1)f(e_2)$. Perhaps there is an energy related aspect of the scattering etc. In fact, it seems one may generalize $f(e_i)$ to $g(f(e_i),e_i)$.

In such a case ((1a)) becomes:

$$g(f(e_1),e_1) g(f(e_2), e_2) = g(f(e_3),e_3) g(f(e_4),e_4) \quad ((3a))$$

Taking \ln of both sides of ((3a)) and equating to energy or $-1/T(e_i-u)$ where u is the chemical potential yields:

$$g(f(e_i),e_i) = \exp(-1/T (e_i-u)) \quad ((4))$$

Thus, $g(f(e_i),e_i)$ behaves as the "independent probability" and not $f(e_i)$ in this case.

A question arises as to the interpretation of the Gibbs ensemble. The original statistical mechanical argument for an ensemble (1) seems to start with:

$W! / [m_1! m_2! \dots]$ ((5a)) where m_i = the number of systems in the ensemble with energy m_i and

$$\text{Sum over } i \text{ } m_i = M \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Sum over } i \text{ } m_i E_i = E \quad ((5a))$$

The systems in the ensemble are completely independent. Each system is composed of many particles. The next step is to generalize ((5a)) to a complex function (see 1) and perform a contour integration near at a saddle point. The fundamental result is that one evaluates:

$\exp(-\sum_i f_i \ln f_i)$ ((6)) at the saddle point which is Shannon's entropy to the power of e .

From this calculation, one proceeds to obtain the system weight $\exp(-E/T)$ ((7)) used in the canonical distribution. (See 1 and 2). E/T arises from the integral over space phase of $\sum_i -f_i \ln(f_i)$ where $\ln(f_i) = \ln(A) - e_i/T$ where A is a normalization constant. Thus, the $\exp(-E/T)$ weight in statistical mechanics is a direct result of the form of Shannon's entropy.

This weight may be generalized for the grand canonical partition function $\exp(-1/T(E-uN))$ where u is the chemical potential. An issue which arises is that one typically uses:

$E = \sum_i e_i n_i$ where n_i is the number of particles in energy state e_i . ((8))

Thus, each single particle acts with an independent $\exp(-e_i/T)$ in the factor ((7)). $\exp(-e_i/T)$, however, is the MB result which is still used in the calculation of the FD and BE distributions from the grand canonical distribution by summing over different occupation numbers using $\exp(-(e_i-u) n_i/T)$. The point we wish to make is that in the generalized case $g(f(e_i), e_i) = \exp(-(e_i-u)/T)$, this does not seem to be appropriate. The starting point ((5a)) for ensembles, however, seems to be completely general and makes no assumptions about the systems except that they be independent. Thus, it seems one cannot keep the assumption of independence, because the usual canonical or grand canonical partition should not hold here.

A New Entropy?

Equation ((6)) shows that Shannon's entropy to the power of e appears in the saddle point integration of ((5a)). One may also consider this identical function in a different way. Imagine one has independent particles with a probability distribution $f(e_i)$. If there are N such particles and N is very large (2) argues that the probability for a $n_i = N f(e_i)$ particles in state e_i is:

$\text{Prob}(\text{macrostate}) = \text{Product over } i \ f(e_i)^{N f(e_i)}$ ((9))

Taking \ln of both sides of ((9)) yields $N \sum_i f(e_i) \ln f(e_i)$. This may be maximized subject to the constraint $\sum_i n_i e_i$ yielding the MB distribution.

In the generalized case, it seems $g(f(e_i), e_i)$ may represent the independent probability, and not $f(e_i)$. In such a case, ((9)) may become:

$\text{Prob}(\text{macrostate}) = \text{Product over } i \ g(e_i)^{N f(e_i)}$ ((10))

This, it seems, would yield a different entropy than Shannon's i.e.

-Sum over i $f(e_i) \ln[g(e_i)]$ which may be maximized subject to Sum over i $e_i f(e_i)=E$

Then one obtains:

$$f \frac{d}{df} \ln(g) + \ln(g) + 1/T (e_i - u) = 0 \quad ((11))$$

If one assumes that $\ln(g)=\text{constant}$, one obtains: $\ln(g) = -1/T e_i$ which is the same result as the two body scattering case: ((4))

Generalized FD and BE Cases

The question now becomes: How does one deal with fermions and bosons? By using two body scattering, we argue one may retain a physical picture of such effects, namely a fermion cannot scatter into an occupied state and the probability for a boson to scatter into an occupied state with n identical bosons is enhanced by $n+1$ (3). Thus, we suggest that ((3a)) is modified:

For fermions

$$g(f(e_1), e_1) [1-f(e_3)] g(f(e_2), e_2) [1-f(e_4)] = g(f(e_3), e_3) [1-f(e_1)] g(f(e_4), e_4) [1-f(e_2)] \quad ((12a))$$

$$\text{So: } \ln\{ g(f(e_i), e_i) / [1-f(e_i)] \} = -1/T (e_i - u)$$

For bosons

$$g(f(e_1), e_1) [1+f(e_3)] g(f(e_2), e_2) [1+f(e_4)] = g(f(e_3), e_3) [1+f(e_1)] g(f(e_4), e_4) [1+f(e_2)] \quad ((12b))$$

$$\ln\{ g(f(e_i), e_i) / [1+f(e_i)] \} = -1/T (e_i - u)$$

Thus, knowing the function $g(f(e), e)$ from the "physics" of the situation one may solve ((3a)), ((12a)) and ((12b)) to obtain the generalized MB, FD and BE distributions.

In order to obtain examples, one may choose different mathematical forms for $g(f(e), e)$ and test these.

Generalized Canonical and Grand Canonical Partition Functions?

For the non-generalized MB, FD and BE cases, one may obtain distributions by either using time reversal two body elastic scattering balance or the canonical/grand canonical partition function. We have argued above that the usual canonical/grand canonical partition function does not hold in the generalized case. It may also be noted from ((12a)) and ((12b)) that even in

the generalized case, the fermion $(1-f(e_i))$ factor and the boson $(1+f(e_i))$ factors are unchanged. In the nongeneralized case, the grand canonical approach yields for fermions:

$$\langle n_i \text{ FD} \rangle = [1 \exp(-1/T(e_i-u)) + 0 \exp(-1/T(e_i-u))] / [\exp(-1/T(e_i-u)) + \exp(-1/T(e_i-u))]$$

And for bosons:

$$\langle n_i \text{ BE} \rangle = [\text{Sum over } n \quad n \exp(-n/T(e_i-u))] / [\text{Sum over } n \quad \exp(-n/T(e_i-u))]$$

The numerator above is a geometric series for which the sum is known and ultimately leads to a $1/[1-\exp(-1/T(e_i-u))]$ factor. (The denominator is a constant normalization factor.)

For the generalized case, one has from ((12a)) and ((12b)):

$$g(f(e),e) \pm \exp(-1/T(e-u)) f = \exp(-1/T(e-u)) \quad \text{where } + \text{ is FD and } - \text{ BE ((13))}$$

This is no longer simply linked to counting of states even though the same factors $(1-f(e_i))$ and $(1+f(e_i))$ are still used in the scattering approach as the basic restriction or enhancement for fermions or bosons (which is based on physics) still holds. (It should be noted that in the scattering case, for FD a factor of $1-f(e_i)$ is used, but the distribution is $1/[1+\exp(-1/T(e_i-u))]$. A similar result holds for the BE case. This is related to function-inverse function pairs.)

In the nongeneralized MB case, one may integrate Shannon's entropy density to obtain:

$$S = -\text{Integral phase space} \sum \text{over } i \quad f_i \ln(f_i) \quad \text{where } f_i = A \exp(-e_i/T)$$

Then: $S = 1/T E - \ln(A)$ ((14)). This accounts for the system weight factor $\exp(-E/T)$ used in the canonical and ultimately grand canonical partition function.

In a section above, we argued that for the generalized case, Shannon's entropy may possibly be changed to: $-\sum \text{over } i \quad f_i \ln(g)$. In such a case, the integral would yield:

$S_{\text{general}} = -\text{Integral phase space} \sum \text{over } i \quad f(e_i) \ln(g(f(e_i),e_i))$. This result might then be used in a weight function of a partition function i.e. $\exp(-S_{\text{general}}/T)$.

This approach, however, seems to be more complicated than a time reversal two body elastic scattering balance. In (4), a different generalized approach is used which makes use of a generalized grand canonical partition function.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have tried to generalize the time reversal two body elastic scattering balance approach to obtain the MB, FD and BE distributions. For the MB case, we replace $f(e_i)$ with $g(f(e_i), e_i)$ and then use $g(1)g(2)=g(3)g(4)$ and $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. For the FD and BD cases, we introduce appropriate $(1-f(e_i))$ or $(1+f(e_i))$ factors to account for scattering restrictions or enhancements. We argue the usual canonical or grand canonical approach which follows from a Gibbs ensemble, uses Shannon's entropy and yields the weight factor $\exp(-E/T)$ where E is the energy of system, no longer holds. We suggest a new generalized entropy and argue that a new weight factor might result from the integral of the new entropy, but argue time reversal balance approach seems more physical and straightforward.

References

1. Huang, Kerson. Statistical Mechanics (Wiley, 1987) pages 193-199
2. Rioul, O. This is IT: A Primer of Shannon's Entropy and Information 2018
<http://www.bourbaphy.fr/rioul.pdf>
3. Feynman R. Lecture Notes.
https://www.feynmanlectures.caltech.edu/III_04.html
4. Treumann, R. and Baumjohan, W. Beyond Gibb-Boltzmann-Shannon: generalized entropies -The Gibbs Lorentzian Example Frontiers of Physics Aug. 14, 2014
<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fphy.2014.00049/full>